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Economics

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Brazil Country Report

(ES12002: Coursework)

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Introduction

Brazil plays a crucial role both regionally and internationally, holding the 11th largest GDP worldwide and the largest in South America. Due to its abundance of natural resources, the country is a dominant agricultural exporter, a giant in mining and a huge energy producer through its productions of biofuels and renewables. Brazil is also a leader in manufacturing sectors like automotive and aeronautics, and it has a well-established financial sector. As a member of BRICS, Brazil is a key player among emerging economies with its largest trade partner being China.

The following country report investigates Brazil’s macroeconomic state, its recent macro-economic revolution and the countries long term challenges and solutions with respect to macro issues.

The Macroeconomic state of the economy

Key Economic indicators

GDP and Growth

The Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) measures the Gross Domestic Product (GDP: The monetary measure of all goods and services produced within a certain time frame) of Brazil quarterly. Brazil is the largest economy in Latin America with a GDP of US\$ 2.19 trillion (International Monetary Fund, 2021), however, GDP per capita remains \$10,300, below Argentina but remaining above Colombia, as seen in Figure 1.

Brazil’s GDP growth has been volatile due to external shocks, such as the 2008 financial crisis and internal factors like inflation. In 2009, growth fell to -0.1% after a strong 5.1% in 2008. More recently, growth has been constrained by political uncertainty and falling export prices, from Figure 2.

Figure 1: GDP per Capita, Data Source: IMF DataSets, 2021

Figure 2: Brazil Real GDP Growth %, Data Source: IMF DataSets, 2021

Inflation

Inflation is the rate at which the average prices for goods and services in an economy rise over time. Brazil currently has an inflation rate of 4.3% (International Monetary Fund, 2021) with the National Monetary Council setting the target rate at 3% +/-1.5%, displayed in Figure 3 below. The Extended Consumer Price Index (IPCA) is the primary measure used for monetary policy, while the National Consumer Price Index (INPC) highlights inequality by focusing on families earning 1-5 times the minimum wage.

In Figure 4, inflation peaked at 2497% in 1990 due to high external debt and budget deficits. The Plano Real in 1994 introduced a new currency (BRL) and tighter monetary measures, reducing inflation to 15.8% by 1996. Inflation has since stabilized, peaking at 14.7% in 2003 during political instability. This high inflation caused huge drops in both consumer and business confidence, as well as a reduction in consumers' purchasing power.

Figure 3: Inflation (period 2000-2024), Data Source: World Bank, 2023

Figure 4: Inflation (Period 1980-2024), Data Source: World Bank, 2023

Unemployment and Labour force participation

Employment in Brazil has seen fluctuating levels over the previous 40 years, as seen in Figure 5 below. The 2023 rate of labor force participation (the percentage of those between the ages of 15 and 64 who are in work) sits at 62.8% (International Monetary Fund, 2021), with the unemployment rate being comparatively low at 6.2% in October 2024 (Banco Central Do Brasil, 2024a). The unemployment rate has seen many different peaks since 1990, especially during the deindustrialization of the 1990s, and the recessions of 2014 and 2020, hitting peaks of 13.9% and 14.9% respectively, as well as only 49.4% of the working age population being in work in 2020 (Sott , et al., 2022). Despite falling from 46.1% in 2011, Brazil also has a large informal sector, with informal employment at 37% in 2023, as displayed in Figure 6 below (International Labour Organization , 2024b). This provides Brazil with many problems, with this unregulated section of the economy delivering decreased tax revenue (weakening Brazil’s already problematic fiscal position), increased poverty and inequality, as well as lower productivity, reducing the nation’s output.

Figure 5: Unemployment rate, Data Source: IMF DataSets, 2021

Figure 6: Informal Employment by Sex, Data Source: ILOSTAT data explorer, 2024

Sectoral Analysis

Economies consist of three key sectors: Primary (agriculture, forestry, and fishing), Secondary (Industry) and Tertiary (Services). For over 20 years, the service sector has been the largest contributor to GDP, accounting for around 60% of value added to GDP (as shown in Figure 7). This sector includes retail, tourism, and financial services, driven by urbanization and a growing middle class. Brazil is a global leader in agribusiness, exporting primary goods including soybeans, coffee and beef whilst maintaining the lowest sector contributing towards GDP growth at 5% value added, illustrating the risks upon the global volatile commodity market. Brazil's secondary sector includes manufacturing steel and cars, in which it was a competing contributor to the service sector until 1990 through a severe decline from 40% to 20%, due to the foreign exchange crisis and the periods of high inflation from 1981-2008 (Feijó & Lamonica, 2012).

Figure 7: Key Sectors, Data Source: World Bank Data, 2023

Figure 9: Brazil's imports, Data Source: OEC, 2022

Regional Economic Disparities within Brazil

Brazil faces significant regional disparities with inequalities between the south and north, with the south accounting for a significant percentage of GDP and manufacturing with cities such as São Paulo, Rio de Janeiro and Minas Gerais being economic powerhouses. Though segregation from south is demonstrated in the north by high levels of poverty, and disparities in the share of labor as *the top decile of the income distribution is 40 percent of the labor income of all Brazilians, and that of the top 1 percent is 12 percent* (Góes, 2019). The disparities stem from historical factors of unequal investment and infrastructure gaps within the economy with efforts to reduce this inequality through progressive taxation on income (a tax increase imposed on workers in correlation with their levels of income) and government provision of schools, boosting levels of education in the north.

How Brazil dealt with recent global shocks

Brazil's 2014 Recession: Global Shocks and Economic Turmoil

From mid-2014 to late 2016, a cascade of fiscal mismanagement, political instability and global commodity supply shocks yielded one of Brazil's most severe economic crises (BBC News, 2017). Real GDP contracted by 3.5% in 2015 and 3.3% in 2016 before showing signs of recovery, highlighted in Figure 10 below (PWT, 2023)

Figure 10: Brazil Real GDP at constant 2017 national prices, Data Source: Penn World Table, 2023

Corruption, fiscal mismanagement, and investment

In the period leading up to 2014, corruption, political instability, and fiscal mismanagement severely hampered domestic and international investment in Brazil. Operation Car Wash was a probe into the state-run energy company Petrobras, with the investigation exposing a vast network of corruption involving executives and politicians up to the highest level (BBC News, 2018). Furthermore, President Dilma Rousseff's government significantly increased public spending which was unmatched by equivalent increases in revenue. The excessive spending led to a rapid rise in public debt and fiscal deficits.

This volatile political landscape and the government's inability to balance its books deterred domestic and foreign investment. Looking below at Figure 11 displaying Brazil's gross fixed capital formation at current purchasing power parities (GFCF), which is the total value of acquisitions minus disposals of fixed assets over a year, there was

roughly a 30% decrease in GFCF in 2014, visualizing the notable reduction in Brazilian investment during this period before stabilising in 2016.

Figure 11: Brazilian Share of gross capital formation at current PPPs, Data Source: Penn World Table, 2023

The Multiplier Effect

As a result of reduced investment, firms couldn't produce sufficient capital to procure new machinery and infrastructure and create new jobs, overall, reducing production capacity. This invariably leads to lower income for households and reduced consumer spending, which further amplifies the initial reduction in investments' effect on aggregate demand causing a cascading impact. This process is defined as the multiplier effect as a relatively small change in investment leads to a greater than anticipated long-run change in output.

Aggregate demand (AD) is the total demand for goods and services in a market. It is equivalent to $C + I + G + X - M$ with each symbol respectively representing (total) consumption, investment, government expenditure, exports, and imports.

By transposing AD and a perfectly diagonal plot of output=AD on a graph of AD by output, a model is constructed which visualizes the multiplier effect with AD₁ being the Brazilian economy's initial AD before the negative investment shock. Market equilibrium can be inferred from the plot where AD and output=AD intersect as at this point the market is able to clear.

By substituting an economy's investment and consumption functions, $I(r)$ and $(C_0 + C_1Y)$ (where C_0 is autonomous consumption that is independent of current income and C_1Y is marginal propensity to consume, which is consumption depending on current income levels (Y) and also accounting for taxes on consumption where τ represents the tax rate), the AD model can be rewritten as the below equation.

$$AD = (C_0 + I(r) + G + X) + (C_1(1 - \tau) - M)Y$$

The equation can be interpreted as a linear function with $(C_0 + I(r) + G + X)$ being the Y-intercept, which is autonomous AD, and $(C_1(1 - \tau) - M)$ being the value of the gradient of the AD function.

When establishing the point of equilibrium by equating the AD function to GDP (Y), the resulting change in output from a change in autonomous demand can be inferred as autonomous demand $(C_0 + I(r) + G + X)$ multiplied by $\frac{1}{(1 - C_1(1 - \tau) + M)}$ which is the overall multiplier on the change in output from the initial change in autonomous demand. See the below equation.

$$Y^* = \frac{1}{(1 - C_1(1 - \tau) + M)} (C_0 + I(r) + G + X)$$

A reduction of R in the investment function $I(r)$ reduces the autonomous AD, meaning less available capital and income for workers, resulting in reduced productivity. In *model 1*, this is represented by AD_2 , with a resulting fall in the y-intercept by a total of R , which can be inferred as the initial reduction in investment in the Brazilian economy in 2014.

This vertical decrease in AD_2 results in a point out of equilibrium as $AD < output$, hence output is reduced. The amount output is reduced by is dependent on the value of the multiplier, specifically the changes in variables: C_1 , τ and M . When the multiplier value is greater than 1, a fall in spending leads to a disproportionately larger decline in output and GDP. However, it also means that smaller increases in spending can have a significant positive effect on the economy.

Government intervention, primarily in increasing government spending, lowers the multiplier effect by substituting for the loss in another variable contributing to autonomous consumption, hence dampening fluctuations. Transfers, like unemployment insurance and social security, also help households' smooth consumption. However, in the case of Brazil in the 2014 recession, it was in the economy's best interest for the government to attempt to substitute for that lost investment to reduce the multiplier effect in the short term. This intervention is witnessed in *model 2* where the economy shifts from point G to H where it partly recovers from the negative investment shock.

Seen in Figure 12, the federal government's expenditures increased by around 11% from 2014 to 2016 to stimulate the economy and reduce the negative impact of the reduction in private investment in the short term.

Figure 12: Brazilian government share of consumption at current PPPs, Data Source: Penn World Table, 2023

To stabilise the country's political front and ultimately restore investor sentiment, Brazilian president Dilma Rousseff was removed from office in 2016 due to the growing allegations of fiscal misconduct, corruption, and illegal accounting practices. Michel Temer, who succeeded Rousseff, introduced reforms aimed at restoring fiscal discipline, which helped stabilise deteriorating confidence in Brazil's markets. This was essential for

stabilizing bond markets and improving investor confidence to increase aggregate demand in the long term.

Inflation & Currency Depreciation

In the period between 2014 to 2016, currency depreciation, rising prices for imported goods, and domestic economic inefficiencies produced consistent inflation. In 2015, the inflation rate was 10.67%, breaching the upper limit of the central bank's target range (Banco Central do Brasil, 2024e). To reduce inflation, the central bank hiked interest rates to make borrowing more expensive and hence curb domestic demand.

The depreciation of the Brazilian Real reduced the value of domestic assets, leading to significant capital outflows, as international investors withdrew from the Brazilian economy in favour of more attractive markets. Hiked interest rates made domestic assets more attractive to international investors due to more enticing returns, ultimately, increasing demand for the Real and stabilising its value.

The Global Impact of COVID-19 on Brazil's Economy

COVID-19 first arrived in Brazil in February 2020, severely impacting Brazil's economy, also reporting 699,310 deaths, ranking second globally in the number of casualties (The New York Times , 2023). Brazil's GDP fell as consumption declined by 11.3% in the second quarter of 2020 (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2020) while experiencing a negative growth rate of -3.3% in 2020 (World Bank, 2023a) due to a loss of consumer confidence as unemployment and poverty both increased. This rise in unemployment during COVID-19 is evident in Figure 13, where in 2018, prior to the pandemic, unemployment was 12.3%. By 2020, it rose to 13.7% whereby this rise in unemployment worsened the pre-existing regional inequality in the north and northeast regions by mostly affecting vulnerable groups of people, in which the majority worked in the service industry or the informal sector. However, by 2023 unemployment decreased to 7.95%. Along with increased unemployment, inflation also rose during the pandemic and peaked in 2021 at 8.3% (World Bank, 2023d) compared to 3.2% in 2020 (World Bank, 2023d) due to several factors across different industries, for example, the rise in price in hydropower, Brazil's main energy source.

Figure 13: Unemployment in Brazil (period 2018-2023), Data Source: World Bank, 2023

During the pandemic, global oil demand fell sharply, however Brazil was the only South American country to increase crude oil production in 2020 (Kempkey & Peterson, 2021). Despite declining oil industry investment since 2019 and Covid-19's demand shock, Petrobras reversed planned production cuts due to rising Chinese demand (Slattery, 2020). Brazil is projected to be the world's fifth-largest crude oil exporter by 2030 (The Rio Times, 2021)

The Real's devaluation led to higher import costs, creating inflationary pressure in Brazil, resulting in investors demanding higher yields to compensate for the expected inflation. Additionally, the combination of global market uncertainty and rising debt in Brazil led to investors losing confidence creating capital outflows due to investors shifting towards safer assets like US Treasuries. This resulted in lower demand for Brazilian bonds and therefore driving up yields. To combat inflation the central bank increased interest rates to 13.75% by September 2022 (Ayres, 2022), which also aided in higher bond yields due to investors requiring returns that matched the interest rate. Economic instability and market volatility, caused by the devaluation and rising debt, required the central bank to repurchase government bonds to boost liquidity and reduce bond yields.

The pandemic disrupted international trade, with exports declining by 7.4% due to reduced manufacturing output and imports dropping by 14.7% as consumption fell (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2021). Therefore, the

balance of payments improved, aided by the Real's devaluation, which boosted agricultural exports and reduced demand for dollar-denominated imports.

To help struggling families, the government launched “Auxilio Emergencial” in 2020, offering up to R\$1,200 for single-parent households and reaching 68 million citizens, costing R\$350 billion (Serviços e Informações do Brasil (Services and Information of Brazil), 2022) Tax relief for small firms and the removal of import duties on medical equipment provided further support. In 2021, the Bolsa Familia program was revamped into Auxilio Brasil, ensuring long-term financial support of at least R\$600 per eligible family.

To address economic strain, Brazil adopted an expansionist approach, increasing public spending to support emergency services, businesses, and workers. This raised the public deficit to 13.7% of GDP and gross public debt to 88.8% of GDP by 2020, up from 74.3% in 2019 (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2021)

Macroeconomic challenges that Brazil face in the future

Fiscal Struggles

Since its transition to a democracy in 1985, Brazil has faced persistent economic challenges, from hyperinflation in the early 1990s to ongoing inequality. Among these, fiscal issues, stemming from a complex tax system and rigid public spending, have consistently undermined economic stability, and contributed to a rising debt burden.

From 2013 to 2021, Brazil's debt to GDP ratio increased significantly, experiencing two different recessions (two successive quarters of negative growth) within eight years, both requiring fiscal intervention. However, decreasing tax revenues and rigid spending has increased the debt, as seen in Figure 14, going from 59.6% in 2013 to high of 96% in 2020, and sitting at 87.6% in 2024 (International Monetary Fund, 2021). This poses as a huge short-term issue for Brazil, (with potential for long term implications) placing constraints on Brazil's future fiscal policy, therefore limiting the production potential of the economy. Additionally, it is looking likely that the government's primary balance won't see a surplus until at least 2029 (Wolf, 2024).

Figure 14: Government Debt, Data Source: IMF DataSets, 2021

During the 2014 recession, conflicting fiscal policies under President Rousseff (cuts in discretionary spending while maintaining nominal wage growth) led to a 3.1% decline in tax revenue between 2015 and 2016. Key revenue sources, such as import duties, fell by 25.9%, while financial operations taxes dropped by 10.9%. Consequently, Brazil recorded one of its highest nominal public sector deficits since the Plano Real in 1994, with the deficit reaching 10.2% of GDP in 2015 (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2017). This led to increased government borrowing, as shown in Figure 15, with public sector borrowing amounting to 9.3% of GDP in 2015.

Figure 15: General Government net lending/borrowing, Data Source: IMF DataSets, 2021

Despite the introduction of a spending cap (PEC 55) in 2017, which limited government spending growth to the rate of inflation, Brazil's debt continued to rise. By 2020, the

Covid-19 pandemic caused a nominal public deficit of 13.7% of GDP, with government revenue falling by 13.1% (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2021). Significant spending on social programs contributed to this, including R\$42 billion allocated to the Ministry of Health (World Health Organization , 2020) and a total Covid-19 response cost of R\$322 billion (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2021).

This surge in borrowing has driven up interest payments, compounded by Brazil's high interest rate of 12.25%. Over the 12 months to October 2024, nominal public sector interest payments totaled R\$869.3 billion, or 7.57% of GDP (Banco Central Do Brasil, 2024c). Economist Felipe Camargo estimates that it could take over 20 years to repay the debt increase from 2020 as a percentage of GDP (Aldaya, 2020).

High debt levels pose long-term challenges, reducing public sector spending capacity in areas like poverty, healthcare, and social inequality while risking a debt spiral. Additionally, this debt has eroded economic confidence, deterring domestic and foreign investment. Addressing Brazil's fiscal imbalances is essential to resolve the issue and restore economic stability.

One of the key contributors to Brazil's fiscal challenges is its inefficient, complex, and regressive tax system, which has remained largely unchanged since the 1960s. Unlike most emerging economies, where income and corporate taxes form the bulk of tax revenue, Brazil disproportionately relies on taxes on goods and services, as seen in Figure 16 below. In 2019, taxes on goods and services contributed 43.6% (R\$1,4048.3 billion) of total revenue, compared to just 22.4% (R\$536.9 billion) from income taxes, significantly below the OECD average of 33.8% (Orair, 2020). This reliance on consumption taxes makes the economy highly vulnerable to both domestic and external commodity shocks, as evident during the 2014 recession.

Figure 16: Tax Revenue Breakdown - In Brazilian Real (R\$), Data Source: UNDP LAC PDS, 2020

Moreover, the regressive nature of Brazil’s tax system has exacerbated inequality. Consumption taxes impose a disproportionately higher burden on lower-income households, worsening income inequality and placing additional pressure on government spending. These structural issues have long hindered fiscal efficiency and economic equity.

Brazil is looking to solve this issue that is hampering the economy. For example, the Constitutional Amendment 132/2023, put forward in December 2023, will combine 5 different taxes on goods and services into 2 taxes, creating a dual VAT system (Edicom, 2024). This reduces the complexity of taxation, as well as promoting growth and investment with less costs and increased tax rebates for firms, especially for exporting firms, whose products are exempt from taxes, making them cheaper and more appealing to foreign consumers. Moreover, this reform has the potential to help with inequality, as this change inputs a destination-based tax model, so tax is collected in the area it is consumed in, rather than where it was produced. This means that areas of lesser wealth will receive more of this tax revenue, therefore improving the living standards in that area.

Structural Economic Imbalance

Brazil’s President Lula da Silva supports a BRICS-wide currency, aiming to stabilize trade prices and reduce reliance on the US dollar (used in 80% of global trade). This would also reduce the inefficiency in trade with Brazil and trading economies, eliminating the fluctuations between individual currencies. Through this, investment and trading would become more predictable, though experts say it may be an uphill battle

(Sullivan, 2023) (Smith, 2025). Investment in Brazil has been fluctuating between 2.5%-4% of GDP (Banco Central do Brasil, 2024b) forming an economic imbalance to compete with dominating economies. In order to remain competitive growth needs to be seen within the economy, but a lack of stable investment within firms could cap the GDP growth rate.

Figure 17: Direct Investment Liabilities (% of GDP), Data Source: Banco Central Do Brasil, 2024

Economies forming a common currency may be at risk to devaluing their terms of trade. This was experienced by the Euro which lost 30% of its value against the US dollar in only a year after coming into effect, reducing the terms of trade of economies (Jeffery, 2003). Greece and other south-eastern European economies faced negative consequences from being in a currency union, as the severe debt crisis in these countries could not be effectively addressed through monetary policy. This was because other eurozone economies required opposite monetary measures to maintain stability. This led the European Central Bank to issue bonds and other debt instruments to raise funds whilst the Greek program was aimed to restore sustainability of the Greek fiscal situation and increase the competitiveness of their markets (Alogoskoufis, 2012). The introduction of a combined currency within BRICs could experience the same impact as China and Russia may need differing monetary policies compared to others within BRICs, which may push Brazil’s debt crisis to the side, limiting the GDP growth more than before the currency was in effect.

Inequality

Inequality remains a persistent challenge for Brazil, with a Gini index of 52.9 (2021) ranking it among the most unequal countries globally. The Gini index measures wealth inequality, where 0 represents perfect equality and 100 indicates extreme inequality. Historical factors, including the legacy of slavery, contribute to entrenched disparities in income, education, and access to resources. Therefore, “while a Danish family in the lowest-income group needs only two generations to achieve an average income level, in Brazil, families in the equivalent group would require nine generations” (Bertolin, 2022)

Income inequality can hinder Brazil’s economic growth, as higher-income individuals save more and spend less, due to their low marginal propensity to consume, reducing overall consumption and limiting GDP growth. A lack of state provided education has left many families in a poverty trap, where children are unable to gain the skills and qualifications, they need in order to earn a higher income. In 2019, 1.1 million children were out of school, aged between 4-5 and 15-17, which is when being in education is not compulsory (UNICEF, 2021). This reduces Brazil’s human capital limiting productivity and therefore economic growth.

Programs like Bolsa Familia have lifted 28 million people out of poverty (Oxfam, no date). In 2003 the Bolsa Família programme, or family scholarship programme, which aimed to provide a minimum level of income to extremely poor families whose monthly income per capita is under R\$150 (\$US47) (Sabry, 2016), providing short-term poverty relief by helping families afford necessities. The programme also includes conditions the recipients must follow in order to qualify for the payments, for example keeping their children in school and preventative healthcare visits for children. This aims to address Brazil’s inequality problem long-term by breaking the poverty trap. However, progress has been slow and at its current rate it will take 75 years for Brazil to reach the inequality level of the United Kingdom (Oxfam, no date)

Brazil’s current tax system is regressive, which undermines any effort to redistribute income. As of 2019, almost half of its tax revenues came from indirect taxes (taxes on goods and services) (Orair, 2020) This system disproportionately affects low-income individuals, as taxes on goods take up a larger share of their income. Despite efforts to change this system, it is a massive challenge for Brazil to fix this issue, and will likely take many years to solve, for example, the Constitutional Amendment 132/2023 (only a small fix in a complicated system) being fully implemented in 2033 (Edicom, 2024).

Conclusion

Brazil has an exciting economic future, with many indicators, like GDP per capita, unemployment, and inflation all showing improvements in the upcoming years. Despite this, Brazil faces many problems, like inequality, regional disparity, fiscal struggles, and its reliance on international trade. Since its change to a democracy in 1985, Brazil has shown great resilience and has tackled many issues, from the hyperinflation of the early 1990s to the politically driven recession of 2014, to the catastrophe of Covid in 2020, displaying its ability to deal with their underlying issues which this report has highlighted. However, Brazil's capability on achieving an improved economic state depends on maintaining a stable government, as well as stability with its trading partners, who can provide Brazil with economic activity to grow the economy.

Bibliography

- Al Jazeera, 2021. *Brazil warns of energy crisis with record drought*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2021/9/1/brazil-warns-of-energy-crisis-with-record-drought>
[Accessed 17 December 2024].
- Aldaya, F., 2020. *Why Brazil's record fiscal deficit could signal trouble ahead*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.spglobal.com/marketintelligence/en/news-insights/latest-news-headlines/why-brazil-s-record-fiscal-deficit-could-signal-trouble-ahead-61061413>
[Accessed December 18 2024].
- Alogoskoufis, G., 2012. *Greece's Sovereign Debt Crisis: Retrospect and Prospect*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.lse.ac.uk/Hellenic-Observatory/Assets/Documents/Publications/GreeSE-Papers/GreeSE-No54.pdf>
[Accessed 12 March 2025].
- Asquith, R., 2020. *Brazil tax measures for COVID-19*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.avalara.com/vatlive/en/vat-news/brazil-tax-measures-for-covid-19.html>
[Accessed 3 December 2024].
- Ayres, M., 2022. *Brazil central bank holds interest rates after 12 straight increases*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/markets/currencies/brazil-central-bank-holds-interest-rates-after-12-straight-increases-2022-09-21/>
[Accessed 6 March 2025].
- Banco Central Do Brasil, 2024a. *Detalhamento do Gráfico - Unemployment rate*. [Online]
Available at:
<https://www.bcb.gov.br/estatisticas/detalhamentoGrafico/graphicstatistics/taxadesocupacao>
[Accessed 22 December 2024].
- Banco Central do Brasil, 2024b. *External sector statistics*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bcb.gov.br/en/statistics/externalsectorstatistics>
[Accessed 18 December 2024].
- Banco Central Do Brasil, 2024c. *Fiscal statistics - Press release - 11.29.2024*. [Online]
Available at:
https://www.bcb.gov.br/content/statistics/fiscalstatistics_prev/202411_Fiscal_statistics_text.pdf
[Accessed 18 December 2024].
- Banco Central do Brasil, 2024d. *Inflation targeting*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bcb.gov.br/en/monetarypolicy/Inflationtargeting>
[Accessed 18 December 2024].
- Banco Central do Brasil, 2024e. *Inflation targeting track record*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bcb.gov.br/en/monetarypolicy/historicalpath>
[Accessed 2 January 2025].
- Banco Central do Brasil, 2024f. *Price indexes*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bcb.gov.br/en/monetarypolicy/priceindex>
[Accessed 18 December 2024].

BBC News, 2017. *Brazil's recession worst on record*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-39193748>
[Accessed 24 12 2024].

BBC News, 2018. *Brazil corruption scandals: All you need to know*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-latin-america-35810578>
[Accessed 1 January 2025].

Bertolin, J. & M. T., 2022. *Equity policies in global and higher education*. [Online]
Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-69691-7_4
[Accessed 27 December 2024].

Briscoe, G. & W. R., 2004. *The impact of human capital on economic growth; a review*. [Online]
Available at:
https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/ier/publications/2003/wilson_and_briscoe_2003.pdf
[Accessed 20 November 2024].

Centre for Public Impact, no date. *Bolsa familia in Brazil*. [Online]
Available at: <https://centreforpublicimpact.org/public-impact-fundamentals/bolsa-familia-in-brazil/>
[Accessed 19 December 2024].

Durán, P. R. F. & Lima, P. C. G. d. C., 2021b. *Work, Inequalities, and Precarization: Impacts on Brazil in Times of COVID-19 Pandemic*. [Online]
Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/interventionseconomiques/14459#tocto1n4>
[Accessed 1 December 2024].

Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2017. *Economic Survey of Latin America and the Caribbean - BRAZIL*. [Online]
Available at: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/13b12a7b-daab-4de0-8a3d-219b3d5fa109/content>
[Accessed 17 December 2024].

Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2020. *Preliminary Overview of the Economies of Latin America and the Caribbean ■ 2020*. [Online]
Available at: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/e846340c-7f8a-4f05-8b66-8f63915aecfa/content>
[Accessed 6 March 2025].

Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 2021. *Economic Survey of Latin America and the Caribbean - BRAZIL*. [Online]
Available at: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/aac760e7-7439-44b2-9a7c-4e69dff7d670/content#:~:text=In%202020%2C%20the%20Brazilian%20public,facing%20the%20Brazilian%20economic%20authorities.>
[Accessed 17 December 2024].

Edicom, 2024. *Brazil's Tax Reform and its impact on electronic invoicing*. [Online]
Available at: <https://edicomgroup.com/blog/brazil-tax-reform#:~:text=Brazil%20recently%20enacted%20tax%20reform,forming%20a%20dual%20VAT%20system.>
[Accessed 20 December 2024].

European Central Bank, 2016. *What is driving Brazil's economic downturn?*. [Online]
 Available at: https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/eb201601_focus01.en.pdf
 [Accessed 7 December 2024].

Feijó, C. A. & Lamonica, M. T., 2012. *The importance of the manufacturing sector for Brazilian economic development*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/267e6729-98c3-4294-8940-f1639dc844f9/content#:~:text=In%20the%20period%201981%2D2008,the%20dynamism%20of%20the%20sector>
 [Accessed 18 December 2024].

Ferragamo, M., 2024. *What Is the BRICS Group and Why Is It Expanding?*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.cfr.org/background/what-brics-group-and-why-it-expanding>
 [Accessed 18 December 2024].

Garcia, M. L. T., 2021. *The COVID-19 pandemic, emergency aid and social work in Brazil*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8261333/>
 [Accessed 3 December 2024].

Góes, C., 2019. *Inequality in Brazil: A Closer Look at the Evolution in States*. [Online]
 Available at:
[https://www.elibrary.imf.org/display/book/9781484339749/ch008.xml#:~:text=Yet%20inequality%20remains%20high%3A%20the,1%20percent%20is%2012%20percent.&text=Indexed%2C%20Brazil's%20income%20distribution%20still,the%20world%20\(Figure%208.2](https://www.elibrary.imf.org/display/book/9781484339749/ch008.xml#:~:text=Yet%20inequality%20remains%20high%3A%20the,1%20percent%20is%2012%20percent.&text=Indexed%2C%20Brazil's%20income%20distribution%20still,the%20world%20(Figure%208.2)
 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Hoyos, M. L., 2020. *Brazil's central bank injects liquidity in financial markets*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://som.yale.edu/blog/brazil-s-central-bank-injects-liquidity-in-financial-markets>
 [Accessed 3 December 2024].

Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística (Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics), 2024. *SCNT - System of Quarterly National Accounts*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.ibge.gov.br/en/statistics/economic/national-accounts/17262-quarterly-national-accounts.html?=&t=noticias-e-releases>
 [Accessed 17 December 2024].

International Labour Organization , 2024a. *Country profiles*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://ilostat.ilo.org/data/country-profiles/>
 [Accessed 20 December 2024].

International Labour Organization , 2024b. *ILOSTAT data explorer*. [Online]
 Available at:
https://rshiny.ilo.org/dataexplorer29/?lang=en&segment=indicator&id=EMP_NIFL_SEX_RT_A&ref_area=BRA
 [Accessed 22 December 2024].

International Monetary Fund, 2021. *Brazil - Datasets*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/BRA>
 [Accessed 10 November 2024].

Jeffery, S., 2003. *The euro: a timeline*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2003/jun/06/euro.eu>
[Accessed 12 March 2025].

Kempkey, N. & Peterson, K., 2021. *Brazil was the only South American country to increase crude oil production in 2020*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.eia.gov/todayinenergy/detail.php?id=50538>
[Accessed 6 March 2025].

Máximo, W., 2024. *Brazil implements new national minimum wage*. [Online]
Available at: <https://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/en/economia/noticia/2024-01/brazil-implements-new-national-minimum-wage>
[Accessed 19 December 2024].

Nassif, A., 2017. *An analysis of Brazil's economic situation: 2014-2017, the short-term outlook and policy alternatives*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.braziliankeynesianreview.org/BKR/article/view/106/77>
[Accessed 2 December 2024].

OECD, 2022. *Brazil (BRA) Exports, Imports and Trading Partners*. [Online]
Available at: <https://oec.world/en/profile/country/bra>
[Accessed 5 January 2025].

Orair, R., 2020. *UNDP LAC PDS No. 43 - The Brazilian Tax System: A Diagnostic Review and Reform Possibilities*. [Online]
Available at: https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2023-12/pds-number43_tributario_brazil_en.pdf
[Accessed 19 December 2024].

Oxfam, no date. *Brazil; extreme inequality in numbers*. [Online]
Available at: : https://www.oxfam.org/en/brazil-extreme-inequality-numbers?utm_source=chatgpt.com
[Accessed 19 December 2024].

PWT, 2023. *University of Groningen, Penn World Table version 10.01*. [Online]
Available at: <https://pwt-data-tool.streamlit.app/>
[Accessed 18 12 2024].

Roberts, E., 2024. *The rebirth of Bolsa Família*. [Online]
Available at: <https://londonpolitica.com/latin-america-watch-blog-list/nc6b59t3gs8n9mxmm393s3z429hepn#:~:text=This%20change%20was%20announced%20by,R%24400%20to%20R%24600>
[Accessed 3 December 2024].

Sabry, S., 2016. *How did Brazil reduce poverty and inequality?*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.madamasr.com/en/2016/01/21/opinion/economy/how-did-brazil-reduce-poverty-and-inequality/>
[Accessed 19 December 2024].

Serdan, T. D., 2020. *COVID-19 in Brazil: Historical cases, disease milestones, and estimated outbreak peak*. [Online]
Available at: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7214305/>
[Accessed 30 November 2024].

Serviços e Informações do Brasil (Services and Information of Brazil), 2022. *Brazil has the largest income transfer program in the world*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.gov.br/en/government-of-brazil/latest-news/2022/brazil-has-the-largest-income-transfer-program-in-the-world>
 [Accessed 3 December 2024].

Slattery, G., 2020. *Brazil's Petrobras cuts production, capex amid coronavirus outbreak*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-petrobras-outlook/brazils-petrobras-cuts-production-capex-amid-coronavirus-outbreak-idUSKBN21D1NW/>
 [Accessed 6 March 2025].

Smith, G., 2025. *Shared Brics money: a basket currency or a basket case?*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.omfif.org/2025/02/shared-brics-money-a-basket-currency-or-a-basket-case/#:~:text=The%20idea%20of%20a%20shared,making%20progress%20will%20be%20challenging.>
 [Accessed 12 March 2025].

Sott , M. K., Bender, M. S. & Baum, K. d. S., 2022. *Covid-19 Outbreak in Brazil: Health, Social, Political, and Economic Implications*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9445630/#section4-00207314221122658>
 [Accessed 21 December 2024].

Sullivan, J., 2023. *A BRICS Currency Could Shake the Dollar's Dominance*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/04/24/brics-currency-end-dollar-dominance-united-states-russia-china/>
 [Accessed 12 March 2025].

Summa, R., 2024. *The Political Economy of Brazilian Inflation*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.phenomenalworld.org/analysis/the-political-economy-of-brazilian-inflation/>
 [Accessed 1 December 2024].

The New York Times , 2023. *Tracking Coronavirus in Brazil: Latest Map and Case Count*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2021/world/brazil-covid-cases.html>
 [Accessed 18 December 2024].

The Rio Times, 2021. *Brazil will be world's fifth largest oil exporter in 2030 – Energy Minister*. [Online]
 Available at: <https://www.riotimesonline.com/brazil-news/brazil/brazil-will-be-the-fifth-largest-oil-exporter-in-2030-minister/>
 [Accessed 6 March 2025].

UNICEF, 2021. *Out-of-school children in Brazil*. [Online]
 Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-69691-7_4
 [Accessed 20 November 2024].

Uno, M., 2024. *EXPANSION OF TRADE AND INVESTMENT BETWEEN BRAZIL AND THE GCC*, s.l.: Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute.

Uno, M., 2024. *THE POTENTIAL OF BRAZIL AS A PARTNER IN THE FOOD AND CLEAN ENERGY SECTORS* —, Tokyo: Mitsui & Co. Global Strategic Studies Institute.

Wolf, M., 2024. *Brazil economic outlook, November 2024*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/economy/americas/brazil-economic-outlook.html>
[Accessed 16 December 2024].

Woody, K., Ustinova, E. & Flake, O., 2020. *Brazilian Agricultural Sector Thrives Despite COVID-19 Pandemic*. [Online]
Available at:
https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Brazilian%20Agricultural%20Sector%20Thrives%20Despite%20COVID-19%20Pandemic%20_Brasilia_Brazil_06-11-2020#:~:text=While%20the%20Brazilian%20economy%20has,attractive%20on%20t
[Accessed 3 December 2024].

World Bank, 2023a. *Food Insecurity and Food Inflation in Brazil*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/brazil/publication/brazil-food-insecurity-and-food-inflation>
[Accessed 1 December 2024].

World Bank, 2023b. *GDP (current US\$) - , Brazil*. [Online]
Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTP.CD?locations=D-BR>
[Accessed 17 December 2024].

World Bank, 2023c. *GDP per capita (current US\$) - Brazil*. [Online]
Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?locations=BR>
[Accessed 17 December 2024].

World Bank, 2023d. *Inflation, consumer prices (annual %) - Brazil*. [Online]
Available at:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/FP.CPI.TOTL.ZG?locations=AR&view=chart>
[Accessed 13 December 2024].

World Bank, 2023e. *Unemployment, total (% of total labor force) (modeled ILO estimate) - Brazil*. [Online]
Available at:
<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.ZS?end=2023&locations=BR&start=2018>
[Accessed 30 November 2024].

World Bank, 2024. *Services, value added (% of GDP) - Brazil*. [Online]
Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NV.SRV.TOTL.ZS?locations=BR>
[Accessed 18 December 2024].

World Health Organization , 2020. *Brazil's response to the COVID-19 pandemic*. [Online]
Available at: https://apps.who.int/gb/COVID-19/pdf_files/13_08/Brazil.pdf
[Accessed 18 December 2024].

World Trade Organization, 2024c. *International Trade Statistics*. [Online]
Available at: <https://stats.wto.org/>
[Accessed 18 December 2024].